

DEVELOPMENT OF DYNAMIC MANAGEMENT SKILLS BASED ON THE CULTURAL CAPITAL OF COMMUNITY TOURISM, PHATTHALUNG PROVINCE

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Abstract

The research of “Development of Dynamic Management Skills Based on the Cultural Capital of Community Tourism, Phatthalung Province” was aimed to develop the dynamic management skills of community-based tourism enterprises in Phatthalung Province. The findings revealed that; (1) Language: the southern language is unique but not as refined as the other languages, (2) Folk literature: Manora or traditional southern performing arts, the identity of Phatthalung Province founding in all areas of the province where the origin of Manora was from Tha Khae Sub-district, Muang District, Phatthalung Province. Many schools in the area will have a Manora transfusion to show the identity of Tha Kae Sub-district as Phatthalung Province is the origin of Manora performing arts, (3) Society, rituals and festivals: in terms of the ritual, there is a belief in Kru Mor Nora or the ancestors of Manora, (4) Original craftsmanship: wisdom and craftsmanship skills, they had made the pottery in the past at Ban Pak Pra, Khuan Khanun District wherein the mountain area, but currently no longer exists, and (5) Thai wisdom sports, gaming and martial arts: most of the sports in Phatthalung Province are related to the traditions as Sud Tom or the traditional southern sport which the provincial administration organization is working to revive. In addition, food training based on the local identity with different contexts needs to be focused and specific to each area due to a difference of raw material sources and dining culture such as a lunch box, etc. which should be conserved. The program should be focused on building service standards and creating added value in the area but still retain the local uniqueness and identity to the tourists in order to increase the income for the local community sustainably.

Keywords: Development, Skill, Dynamic Management, Based on, Cultural Capital, Tourism, Community, Phatthalung Province

Introduction

In 2017, it was a challenging year for Thai tourism to achieve the goal of expanding tourism income to 2.84 trillion baht when the Chinese tour began to decline. The Tourism Authority of Thailand (TAT) by Mr. Yuthasak Supasorn, the Governor revealed that TAT set targets for 2017 by giving more focus on the tourist market in the country with generating income from tourists in the country of 950,000 million baht, an increase of approximately 10%, which will come from the adjustment of the market plan encouraging Thai people to travel. As for the international tourist market, it will grow approximately 10% as well, with total revenue expected to be 1.89 trillion baht, with a focus on increasing the cost per trip from attracting quality tourists. As a result, overall tourism income in 2017 increased by 10% or approximately 2.84 trillion baht.

The market direction in 2017, the TAT still focus on the strength of “Thainess”, a distinctive feature that is different from other countries and being a favorite tourist attraction among tourists who want to experience the authentic Thai by presenting the tourism products

tied with more Thainess to increase the income and strength to the local economy as being a part of tourism and leading to the future sustainable economy, society and tourism. In the previous year, Thai tourism has increased significantly to the Thai economy and resulted in distinctly growth of related businesses with 30 million foreign tourists in 2016, resulting in an increase of 11% in tourism income per GDP, and the number of foreign tourists is expected to expand continuously to over 37 million in 2017. In addition to the income that comes from tourists directly, the tourism industry also posed a positive impact on the overall employment and investment of the country by tourism-driven industries such as hotels and restaurants, wholesale and retail business, and transportation and communications with more than 10 million people employed, or an average annual growth rate of 1.4% and account for 26% of the overall employment.

Phatthalung Province is located in the east of southern Thailand, away from Bangkok along the Asian route (National Highway 41) with a distance of approximately 858 kilometers, a total area of approximately 3,424.473 square kilometers and a population of 524,857. Nowadays, Phatthalung Province Administrative area is divided into 11 districts; Muang Phatthalung District, Khuan Khanun District, Khao Chaison District, Pak Phayun District, Kong Rha District, Ta Mhod District, Pa Bon District, Si Banphot District, Pa Phayom District, Bang Kaeo District and Srinakarin District. The Provincial emblem is Khao Ok Thalu where is a significant tourist attraction, with long stairs from the foothills to the cave and a hole in the middle for tourists to see the scenery of Phatthalung Province widely, but nowadays, it lacks development sustainable as the tourist attraction of the province.

The vision of Phatthalung Province, "City of quality people, good environment, community strength, grow and prosper from the base of agriculture, culture, wisdom and sustainable conservative tourism." A community strength refers to a community where people have a simple way of life, live with the philosophy of a sufficiency economy, being employed, earn a sufficient income to live, have security guarantees, being safe in life and property, being protected by the law equally and fairly, having a human dignity, live in society happily, the culture and traditions of the community are managed strongly, and having the social and economic development value of the community.

Phatthalung Province has defined five strategic issues focusing on strategic issues related to the community. The community strength is set as the first priority in the strategic issue of capacity building in the agricultural sector and downstream industries from agriculture, and community and local products. Nowadays, there is an increasingly dynamic environment, excessive competition and social needs, consequently, the community must be flexible and adaptable to this change and adjust to the crisis as an opportunity. The community enterprise has administrated by the standard framework of the community enterprise to define a guideline for building the community enterprise's strength, but there are some issues from the community and local area in the administration development for their strength and self-reliant as there are other issues; administration of the marketing group and member, administration of the production and support, and administration of the accounting. The community business development towards sustainability, the concept of sustainable development will help the

development of community enterprises by promoting the use of local resources and wisdom with modern knowledge to raise the standard of quality products and services, access to funding and marketing, upgrading potential entrepreneurs towards medium-sized enterprises and can be driven by knowledge, technology and innovation. The concept of sustainable development of community enterprise by focusing on the role of capital in accordance with the concept of sustainable development comprising of four dimensions of capital; physical capital, human capital, social capital, and natural capital, for the strengthening of community-based tourism enterprises, which will be useful to indicate the level of development potential and issues of that community enterprise group, and also be useful to define a guideline for the development of community enterprises by the concept of sustainable development.

Phatthalung Province has defined a strategy to promote tourism in various forms; sea tourism, ecotourism, and historical and cultural tourism, etc., including promoting and supporting the development of products and services related to tourism such as One Tambon One Product (OTOP) in accordance with the era, but still conserving the identity of the community or local area. Phatthalung Province is located in the east of southern Thailand, away from Bangkok along the Asian route (National Highway 41) with a distance of approximately 858 kilometers, a total area of approximately 3,424.473 square kilometers and a population of 524,857. Nowadays, Phatthalung Province Administrative area is divided into 11 districts; Muang Phatthalung District, Khuan Khanun District, Khao Chaison District, Pak Phayun District, Kong Rha District, Ta Mhod District, Pa Bon District, Si Banphot District, Pa Phayom District, Bang Kaeo District and Srinakarin District. The Provincial emblem is Khao Ok Thalu where is a significant tourist attraction, with long stairs from the foothills to the cave and a hole in the middle for tourists to see the scenery of Phatthalung Province widely, But nowadays, it lacks development sustainable as the tourist attraction of the province.

As the importance above, the researcher is interested in studying the Development of Dynamic Management Skills Based on the Cultural Capital of Community Tourism, Phatthalung Province, to support a change of environment and tourist groups for the growth of tourism in Phatthalung Province in all situations including strengthening the villager organization in natural resource and cultural management by the participation process of people in the community for defining the development directions and benefiting from tourism, creating the mutual learning between the landlord and the visitors, building the perception and understanding in a role of the local community towards the natural resource conservation, and encouraging or supporting both natural and cultural conservation.

Objective

1. To study the dynamic potential in tourism management suitable for Phatthalung Province.

Terminology definition

1. **Human capital potential development** refers to an improvement and a change of skills, knowledge, competency and personal qualities in Phatthalung Province.

2. **Dynamic management** refers to an adaptation to the intense competition in the commercial business and a change of a globalized economic society in Phatthalung Province.
3. **Cultural capital** refers to the good things that people in the past think, do, express and inherit through practice both tangible and intangible in Phatthalung Province.
4. **Skill** refers to expertise by keep practicing in various activities of people in Phatthalung Province.
5. **Tourism innovative lifestyle** refers to an experience of lifestyle, living culture, dining culture and community attraction in Phatthalung Province.
6. **Community of Phatthalung Province** refers to a group of people in 4 small areas; mountain, forest, field and sea areas in Phatthalung Province.
7. **Attitudes towards tourism tendency in Phatthalung Province** refers to an evaluation of feelings, behavioral tendency towards qualities and overall benefits of human capital skill development based on the community tourism innovative lifestyle or an idea arising from the behavioral tendency caused by satisfaction or dissatisfaction with something.
8. **Service provider** refers to entrepreneurs, community enterprises and tour service staff in Phatthalung Province.

Methodology

The researcher applied the qualitative research methodology with the processes and methods as follows;

1. Key informants

The key informants comprised of; (1) five souvenir shop entrepreneurs and community enterprises, (2) five government staff in 4 areas; mountain, forest, field and sea areas in Phatthalung Province in order to gather the primary data of 8 programs and select 2 programs per area.

The sample group was 20 persons from both groups of the key informants in 4 areas selected by using the specific method. Data was gathered by using the in-depth interview, focus group interview and observation with the structured interview on the program synthesis.

2. Research instruments

Data was gathered by using the in-depth interview and focus group interview from the key informants in 4 areas; mountain, forest, field and sea areas in Phatthalung Province.

3. Data gathering

Data was gathered by using the in-depth interview and focus group interview from the key informants on human capital skill development based on the community tourism innovative lifestyle.

4. Data analysis

Data were analyzed by recording details and using the content analysis.

Results and Discussion

A study of the dynamic potential of tourism management suitable for Phatthalung Province

1. Language, it revealed that the southern language is unique but not as refined as the other languages such as the northern language and the northeastern language. In terms of hospitality, the language still doesn't feel welcome, but the southern people are kind. On the other hand, the southern language is still a communication barrier between tourists and local people which is consistent with the concept of (Albino, Garavelli and Gorgoglione, 2004); building the human capital by the activity of building or changing behavior for creating value for each person, consistent with the concept of (Davenport, 1999); the human capital will arise from education and practice. In psychology, behavioral adjustment can be carried out through learning and perception processes, parenting, prototyping, and self-improvement, and consistent with the concept of Chatchariya Bailee et al. (2015); a study of Human Capital Potential Development Plan to Strengthen Tourism Management in the Central Northeast towards the ASEAN Economic Community revealed that in terms of language and culture: there were many projects applied such as potential and language skill development of tourism entrepreneur, language skill analysis for local tourism, development plan from cultural diversity, tourist attractions at the historical heritage, image promotion of Central Northeast network, planning for the tourism sector integration to accelerate the liberalization of services in the regional tourism industry including measures to facilitate the travel of tourists.

2. Folk literature, it revealed that (1) Manora or traditional southern performing arts, the identity of Phatthalung Province founding in all areas of the province where the origin of Manora was from Tha Khae Sub-district, Muang District, Phatthalung Province. Many schools in the area will have a Manora transfusion to show the identity of Tha Kae Sub-district as Phatthalung Province is the origin of Manora performing arts. There are tourists visiting Tha Khae to study the history of Manora, fulfilling the vow in the sixth month, and the annual Manora festival competition for the Royal cup of Her Royal Highness Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn which indicated the significance of Manora performing arts in Phatthalung Province, and (2) Nang Talung or traditional shadow play, there are more restrictions on the show than Manora as it must be performed only at night. Consequently, there is a change in the form of showing in order to have more opportunities to perform such as Nang Talung Kon or traditional shadow play by a human, and Nang Talung Talk Show or traditional shadow play by a talk show. In terms of tourism, the participation in tourism is less than Manora as Manora can be performed on many occasions such as welcoming tourists, greetings, and opening ceremonies. Nevertheless, both Manora and Nang Talung still inherit from generation to generation for such teaching young students to learn basic gestures through community or school which is consistent with the concept of (Sarafino, 2001), providing education including providing education for parents and learning resources is explicitly creating human capital, and

the process of understanding and learning will focus on building tacit human capital and behavioral human capital. In both processes, knowledge must be selected in accordance with the creator of human capital and the context of community and society in the use of human capital.

3. Society, rituals and festivals, in terms of the ritual, there is a belief in Kru Mor Nora or the ancestors of Manora such as the Teacher's Day Observation at Aomjitr Manora's House in the third month which all students from many areas will respect their ancestors of Manora. The tourists can attend this ceremony at Tha Kae Sub-district, Phatthalung Province where is the most remarkable ritual of Kru Mor Nora as the origin of Manora performing arts. In the opinion of the interviewee, there are additional activities in this ritual during the festive tourism as it is a short festival and remarkable in only some areas of Phatthalung Province such as Cruising Festival at Pa Phayom District, and Floating Festival which tourists can attend only as seasonal, which is consistent with the concept of (Sarafino, 2001), providing education including providing education for parents and learning resources is explicitly creating human capital, and the process of understanding and learning will focus on building tacit human capital and behavioral human capital. In both processes, knowledge must be selected in accordance with the creator of human capital and the context of community and society in the use of human capital, and consistent with the research of Phrakhru Phothisuwannakun (2019), a study of Social Capital: Guidelines for Promoting Community Tourism of Lao Song Community in Suphanburi Province revealed that; 1. Social capital characteristics of Lao Song community in Suphanburi Province indicated that there are 4 areas of suitable community potential for promoting tourism in Lao Song community: 1) community resource, 2) community organization and leader, 3) self-management and participation, and 4) network and collaboration; 2. Guidelines for promoting community tourism of Lao Song community in Suphanburi Province indicated that the tourism activities in various tourist attractions should create a network linked people or local community organizations with the public sector, private sector and entrepreneurs as a tourism promotion network that is linked to the Lao Song community's way of life and culture in various dimensions: the historical tourism, religious and cultural tourism, and community and natural tourism.

4. Original craftsmanship, wisdom and craftsmanship skills, they had made the pottery in the past at Ban Pak Pra, Khuan Khanun District wherein the mountain area, but currently no longer exists. The basketry such as fishing tools, broom and various tools is not remarkable and almost disappear now, but the weaving of Krajoed in Thale Noi area is remarkable and well-known, woven fabric in Lan Khoi Sub-district, batik fabric in Lampam Sub-district, and coconut shell in Chaiburi Sub-district, etc. which is consistent with the concept of (Sarafino, 2001), providing education including providing education for parents and learning resources is explicitly creating human capital, and the process of understanding and learning will focus on building tacit human capital and behavioral human capital. In both processes, knowledge must be selected in accordance with the creator of human capital and the context of community and society in the use of human capital, and consistent with the research of Phrakhru Phothisuwannakun (2019), a study of Social Capital: Guidelines for Promoting Community Tourism of Lao Song Community in Suphanburi Province revealed that; 1. Social

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5. Thai wisdom sports, gaming and martial arts, most of the sports in Phatthalung Province are related to the traditions as Sud Tom or the traditional southern sport which the provincial administration organization is working to revive. Sud Tom is to put cooked rice in the rattan ball made of coconut leaf or pandanus leaf. Muslim community sports, Wild Likay Dance with playing by fishing gestures, can be seen in Muslim areas such as Kongra District, Pa Bon District, and Mueng District. Additionally, common sports such as sea boxing and eating competition are also can be seen in almost all provinces which is consistent with the concept of (Sarafino, 2001), providing education including providing education for parents and learning resources is explicitly creating human capital, and the process of understanding and learning will focus on building tacit human capital and behavioral human capital. In both processes, knowledge must be selected in accordance with the creator of human capital and the context of community and society in the use of human capital.

A study of patterns and methods for developing dynamic potential in tourism management suitable for Phatthalung Province with participation from all sectors.

1. Transportation system from the city to mountain, forest, field and sea areas

Nowadays, transportation in Phatthalung Province is comfortable due to the tourism network development with many rural roads and electricity for the safety and comfort of the tourists and people in the province. Nevertheless, there is still a lack of road signs which is currently doing a project for road signs in rural roads including bathrooms and restrooms. The local government organization in the main route area has to provide clean restrooms for the public with clearly visible warning signs stating in every 1 kilometer both left and right side before reaching the restroom.

The future project is a project of road signs to facilitate the tourists who travel by themselves for more internationality of Phatthalung Province and speed limit signs for the safety of tourists' driving. As the average occupancy rate in Phatthalung Province was 1.8 nights, it is very small average compared with the convenient transportation and rounded by large cities for such traveling from Phatthalung Province to Hat Yai, Songkhla Province during 20:00 hours, causing tourists rather choose to stay in big cities than in Phatthalung Province but if a tourist prefers peaceful ecological nature, Phatthalung Province is the best lodging destinations.

A future tendency of two direct airports to Phatthalung Province, there are obstacles with flight requirements in terms of distance and area within a radius of 100 kilometers from the major airports in the surrounding areas such as Hat Yai Airport, Trang Airport. Consequently, there may be no airports in Phatthalung Province in the next 10 years.

2. Dynamic potential development of tourism management for sustainability

Training as the integrated network of mountain, forest, field and sea areas by the community-based tourism club as the tourism network in rural areas which is different from the lodging business in Phatthalung Province. The training for lodging business should be appropriate with the identity and context of each area; mountain, forest, field and sea areas. In terms of the community storyteller training, it should create tourism routes; mountain and field areas, field and sea areas, in order to build the mutual tourism route integration for more diversity and interest in all activities.

In addition, food training based on the local identity with different contexts needs to be focused and specific to each area due to a difference of raw material sources and dining culture such as a lunch box, etc. which should be conserved. The program should be focused on building service standards and creating added value in the area but still retain the local uniqueness and identity to the tourists in order to increase the income for the local community sustainably.

Conclusion and Suggestion

1. Providing a balance in management with consideration for (1) Community, the life quality of people in the community has to be improved, (2) Supportive economy, the traditional intellectual capital of the community where is not allowed for the only one entrepreneur to run a business in the area, (3) Ecological conservation, it has to be conserved and passed on to next generations including the community-based tourism must be creative tourism, growing on a cultural capital basis, focus on truly touching the way of life of the community as spiritual tourism to understand the way of life such as the farming life, etc.

2. Building houses for villagers in the community that is a tourist attraction should be allocated space to facilitate tourists to stay as most of them are built a one-story house size for family members with small yard or space, no proportions for the host and guest, some are renovated and modernized. Consequently, it has to study the landscape architecture that is suitable for supporting tourists with raised basement, and river or canal beside the house, etc. There are restrictions on population in bringing villagers to become entrepreneurs as the physical issues in some households and others such as the youth in the community (at the age of 15-25) are not as interested in being a guide as they should, most of them addicted to drugs, not attend school and most of the potential members in the community moved to attend school in Phuket. Initially, the movement in the community as an entrepreneur may have to explore within the community, inquire with the community leader on the possibility of routing.

Nowadays, in Thale Noi, Klong Pak Pra has developed quite large compared to other areas as seen from the opening of new resorts. There is an annual event, "Sailing Thale Noi" which will be held on February 14 – April 14, hosted by the Municipality and the Provincial

Administrative Organization since the time that the key informant worked as the government officials. As a result of this event, tourism of the province gradually grew and made Thale Noi better known, including in the previous time, Her Royal Highness Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn has visited here many times.

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